

Diacido complexes of divalent cadmium and mercury with *N*-(thiobenzoyl)-piperidine and *N*-(*p*-methoxythiobenzoyl)piperidine

Ratan K. Choudhary^{a*}, C. K. Choudhary^a and L. K. Mishra^b

^aP.G. Department of Chemistry, C. M. Science College, Darbhanga-846 004, Bihar, India

E-mail : rkc_56@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 001, Bihar, India

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Abstract : Diacido complexes of Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with *N*-(thiobenzoyl)piperidine (tbp) and *N*-(*p*-methoxythiobenzoyl)piperidine (mtbp) of general formula [Cd₂(tbp)₂X₄] (X = Cl, Br or I), [Hg₂L₂X₄] (L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br or I) and [ML₂X₂] (M = Cd^{II} or Hg^{II}; L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br, I or NCS) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, electrical conductance data, melting point, molecular weight determination, thermal and ¹H NMR and infrared spectral studies. The monoligated complexes have been suggested to be halogen bridged dimeric whereas bisligated complexes possess mononuclear pseudotetrahedral structure.

Keywords : Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, *N*-(thiobenzoyl)piperidine, *N*-(*p*-methoxythiobenzoyl)piperidine, IR, UV, ¹H NMR, TGA.

Introduction

The introduction of sulphur and nitrogen atoms in the structure of organic compounds has often resulted in important consequences in their behaviour towards metal ions. Many investigations have been undertaken of the interaction of metal ions with ligands containing sulphur and nitrogen as donor atoms¹. Substituted thioamides possess various physiological activities² and have been shown to be disinfectants³. Substituted piperidines have antimicrobial⁴ activity. Among heavy metals cadmium and mercury are toxic and dangerous pollutants⁵ and their toxicity is manifested in many different ways. These metals can be enriched by organisms and the type of bonding can be converted to more poisonous metal organic complexes as observed in the transformation of mercury into methyl mercury as happened in the Minimata Bay of Japan where 52 people died after eating mercury contaminated fish⁶. Mercury(II) and cadmium(II) complexes with sulphur donor ligands have been the subject of investigation in recent years due to their fungicidal⁷ and antimicrobial⁸ properties. The physiological activities of metal complexes of substituted thioamides are expected to be enhanced and worth investigating. In pursuance of

synthetic and kinetic studies on piperidine and work on substituted thioamide complexes with ionic metals by some workers⁹, we are reporting preparation and characterization of cadmium(II) and mercury(II) complexes with *N*-(thiobenzoyl)piperidine (tbp) and *N*-(*p*-methoxythiobenzoyl)piperidine (mtbp) (Fig. 1) in the present article.

Y = H or CH₃O-

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The analytical data of the complexes are shown in Table 1. The monoligated complexes [HgLX₂] (L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br or I) and [Cd(tbp)X₂] (X = Cl, Br or I) have lower solubility in methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile and higher melting point than those of corresponding bisligated complexes [HgL₂X₂] and [CdL₂X₂] (L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br, I or NCS), however, both are fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO. The electri-

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Complex (Mol. formula)	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Molecular weight	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
				N	Metal	Halogen
L = <i>N</i> -(thiobenzoyl)piperidine						
[Cd ₂ L ₂ Cl ₄]	Light cream	231	-	3.70	28.69	18.37
[Cd(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS)Cl ₂] ₂				(3.60)	(28.92)	(18.24)
[Cd ₂ L ₂ Br ₄]	Light cream	210	-	2.80	23.28	33.66
[Cd(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS)Br ₂] ₂				(2.93)	(23.53)	(33.46)
[Cd ₂ L ₂ I ₄]	Light cream	191	-	2.31	19.84	44.22
[Cd(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS)I ₂] ₂				(2.45)	(19.67)	(44.41)
[CdL ₂ Cl ₂]	Light cream	184	-	4.54	18.78	11.81
[Cd(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ Cl ₂]				(4.72)	(18.93)	(11.94)
[CdL ₂ Br ₂]	Light cream	167	-	3.93	16.22	23.21
[Cd(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ Br ₂]				(4.10)	(16.46)	(23.40)
[CdL ₂ I ₂]	Light cream	146	-	3.42	14.14	32.46
[Cd(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ I ₂]				(3.61)	(14.47)	(32.67)
[CdL ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Light cream	144	-	8.52	17.22	-
[Cd(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ (NCS) ₂]				(8.76)	(17.59)	
[Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₄]	Light cream	203	946.0	2.81	41.80	15.05
[Hg(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS)Cl ₂] ₂				(2.94)	(42.07)	(14.87)
[Hg ₂ L ₂ Br ₄]	Light cream	186	1118.0	2.59	35.16	27.92
[Hg(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS)Br ₂] ₂				(2.48)	(35.46)	(28.29)
[Hg ₂ L ₂ I ₄]	Light cream	111	1314.0	2.28	30.34	37.82
[Hg(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS)I ₂] ₂				(2.11)	(30.18)	(38.18)
[HgL ₂ Cl ₂]	Cream	176	679.0	4.25	29.66	10.41
[Hg(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ Cl ₂]				(4.11)	(29.41)	(10.39)
[HgL ₂ Br ₂]	Cream	142	-	3.50	25.84	20.51
[Hg(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ Br ₂]				(3.63)	(26.02)	(20.73)
[HgL ₂ I ₂]	Cream	97	858.0	3.07	23.01	29.18
[Hg(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ I ₂]				(3.24)	(23.19)	(29.34)
[HgL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	Cream	93	-	7.57	27.33	-
[Hg(C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NS) ₂ (SCN) ₂]				(7.70)	(27.58)	
L = <i>N</i> -(<i>p</i> -methoxythiobenzoyl)piperidine						
[CdL' ₂ Cl ₂]	Cream	134	-	4.21	16.91	10.64
[Cd(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ Cl ₂]				(4.28)	(17.19)	(10.84)
[CdL' ₂ Br ₂]	Cream	132	-	3.82	15.21	21.30
[Cd(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ Br ₂]				(3.77)	(15.13)	(21.51)
[CdL' ₂ I ₂]	Cream	109	-	3.29	13.38	29.95
[Cd(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ I ₂]				(3.35)	(13.43)	(30.33)
[CdL' ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Cream	135	-	8.28	15.87	-
[Cd(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ (NCS) ₂]				(8.01)	(16.08)	
[Hg ₂ L' ₂ Cl ₄]	Cream	176	1003.0	2.64	38.94	14.10
[Hg(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO)Cl ₂] ₂				(2.76)	(39.58)	(13.99)
[HgL' ₂ Cl ₂]	Cream	137	738.0	3.51	27.22	9.32
[Hg(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ Cl ₂]				(3.77)	(27.02)	(9.55)

Note

		<i>Table-1 (contd.)</i>				
[Hg ₂ L' ₂ Br ₄]	Cream	167	1181.0	2.27	33.43	27.03
[Hg(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO)Br ₂] ₂				(2.35)	(33.67)	(26.82)
[HgL' ₂ Br ₂]	Cream	119	823.0	3.19	24.28	19.15
[Hg(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ Br ₂]				(3.37)	(24.14)	(19.23)
[Hg ₂ L' ₂ I ₄]	Cream	104	1345.0	2.10	29.21	36.69
[Hg(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO)I ₂] ₂				(2.03)	(29.08)	(36.80)
[HgL' ₂ I ₂]	Cream	92	914.0	3.24	21.44	27.28
[Hg(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ I ₂]				(3.03)	(21.68)	(27.44)
[HgL' ₂ (SCN) ₂]	Cream	95	-	7.05	25.22	-
[Hg(C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NSO) ₂ (SCN) ₂]				(7.11)	(25.47)	

cal conductance values of complexes in DMF at 30–31 °C are in the range of 4–12 S cm² mol⁻¹. The negligible electrical conductance value of complexes suggested co-ordinated nature of anions. The complex [HgLX₂] as well as [CdLX₂] (X = Cl, Br or I) have higher melting or decomposition temperature than those of bisligated species. The lower solubility and the higher melting point of monoligated complexes than those of bisligated complexes suggests dimeric or polymeric nature of the former and mononuclear to the latter series of complexes. The melting point of complexes were found in the order Cl > Br > I for both monoligated and bisligated complexes. The melting point order indicates higher covalency of diiodo complexes and this order is in accordance with decreasing electronegativity and increasing polarizability order of halogens. The molecular weight determination of bisligated mercury(II) complexes in benzene correspond to formula Hg₂L₂X₂ (L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br, I or NCS) while those of monoligated products by Rast's method correspond to formula Hg₂L₂X₄ (L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br or I) supporting mononuclear structure to bisligated complexes and dinuclear structure to monoligated products. By analogy similar structures are suggested to the corresponding Cd^{II} complexes.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectrum of *N*-(thiobenzoyl)piperidine displays a number of prominent bands due to various modes of phenyl and piperidine ring vibrations in 1600–400 cm⁻¹ region due to ν(C=C), ν(C–N), ν(C–C), δ(CH₂), ν(C–H), (CH₂) scissoring, (CH₂) out of plane bending, ring deformation vibrations etc. at 1598, 1498, 1442, 1380, 1295, 1248, 1202, 1140, 1080, 1028, 1015, 930, 865, 770, 710, 552, 510, 460 and 410 cm⁻¹. In IR spectra of complexes most of the bands are unaffected. The IR band

located at 1248 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C–N stretch¹⁰ which is shifted to higher frequency and observed at 1250–1265 cm⁻¹ while a medium band at 1015 cm⁻¹ assigned as ν(C=S) vibration is shifted to lower frequency by 15–50 cm⁻¹ in complexes¹¹. The shift of ν(C=S) band to lower frequency in complexes suggests the bonding of ligand through thioketo sulphur^{11,12} which in turn increases the

bond order of (C–N) of (N–C=S) group resulting into red shift of ν(C–N) vibration. The δ(NCS) of ligand is observed at 510 cm⁻¹ and it shifts to lower frequency by 10–20 cm⁻¹ supporting coordination of thione 'S'. The IR spectrum of *N*-(*p*-methoxythiobenzoyl)piperidine displays prominent IR bands at 1604, 1492, 1300, 1238, 1208, 1180, 1140, 1033, 1012, 990, 902, 862, 834, 820, 766, 735, 570, 525 and 485 cm⁻¹. The medium band at 990 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν(C=S) vibration which shifts to lower frequency by 10–30 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination of thione sulphur in complexes. The ν(C–N) of thioamide observed at 1038 cm⁻¹ shifted to higher wave number of 15–30 cm⁻¹ due to coordination of thione sulphur. The (NCS) deformation assigned to a band at 485 cm⁻¹ is also shifted to lower frequency by 5–10 cm⁻¹ supporting the coordination of thioamide group^{11,12}.

The IR spectra of [CdL₂(NCS)₂] (L = tbp or mtbp) display ν(C≡N) at 2040 cm⁻¹ as strong and broad band, ν(C=S) at 805 and 803 cm⁻¹ and δ(NCS) at 495 and 475 cm⁻¹ suggesting 'N' coordination of thiocyanate group in Cd^{II} complexes^{13,14}. The IR spectra of [HgL₂(SCN)₂] (L = tbp and mtbp) display ν(C≡N) as strong and sharp bands at 2122 and 2100, ν(C=S) at 705 and 695 and δ(NCS) at 435 and 432 cm⁻¹ for tbp and mtbp complexes respectively. The position and nature of NCS vibrations suggested the coordination of thiocyanate group through sulphur^{13,14} in Hg^{II} complexes.

In far infrared region, the complexes display one or two new bands located at $370\text{--}305\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and they are tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{M-S})$ vibration^{15,16}. Thus IR spectral studies indicate monodentate coordination of ligands in almost all the complexes.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of *N*-(thiobenzoyl)piperidine (tbp), *N*-(*p*-methoxybenzoyl)piperidine (mtbp) and their complexes were recorded in CDCl₃. The phenyl ring CH proton signals are observed as multiplet $\delta = 7.21\text{--}7.45$ ppm. The piperidine ring (CH₂) proton ¹H NMR peaks were observed in four different regions which suggested chair configuration of piperidine ring in (tbp) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

The protons at ²C and ⁴C carbon display ¹H NMR signals as multiplet (δ 1.81, 4H). The ³C protons signals are located at δ 1.52–1.58 as quintats (2H, *J* 4.93 Hz). The ⁵C and ¹C proton signals are located at down field δ 3.52 and δ 4.35 respectively as triplets for 2H each. The large down field shifting of ¹C protons' peaks suggested that ¹C protons are in the vicinity of thioamide group. In complexes (Table 2) the phenyl group proton peaks are not affected but the piperidine ring ¹C and ⁵C protons (4H) signals are further shifted to down field suggesting coordination of thioamide sulphur of (tbp) with metal atoms. The proton signals for ²C, ³C and ⁴C carbon (6H) in complexes donot get separated suggesting inversion of configuration of piperidine ring from chair to boat form.

The ¹H NMR peaks of benzene protons of (mtbp) occur in two regions as doublet. The signals at δ 7.25 (2H, *d*, *J* 33.3 Hz) is assigned to proton peak adjacent to methoxy (CH₃O-) group. The ¹H NMR signals at δ 6.85 (2H, *d*, *J* 32.3 Hz) are attributed to protons situated near less electronegative substituent (>C=S) group. These signals are not affected appreciably in its complexes. However, slight down field shift of proton signals (δ 6.92) adjacent to thioamide (NCS) group is due to involvement

Table 2. ¹H NMR data of ligands and complexes

Compd.	¹ H NMR (CDCl ₃) δ
tbp	1.52–1.58 (2H, <i>q</i> , <i>J</i> 4.93 Hz, ³ C); 1.81 (4H, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 8.6 Hz, ² C, ⁴ C); 3.52 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 4.18 Hz, ⁵ C); 4.35 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 4.1 Hz, ¹ C); 7.21–7.45 (5H of phenyl ring, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 10 Hz)
mtbp	1.54–1.65 (2H, <i>q</i> , <i>J</i> 3.84 Hz, ³ C); 1.82 (4H, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 5.6 Hz, ² C, ⁴ C); 3.55 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 3.3 Hz, ⁵ C); 3.8 (3H of methoxy proton, <i>s</i>); 4.35 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 5.0 Hz, ⁵ C); 6.85 (2H of phenyl proton adjacent to OCH ₃ , <i>d</i> , <i>J</i> 32.3 Hz); 7.25 (2H of phenyl proton adjacent to thioamide group, <i>d</i> , <i>J</i> 33.3 Hz)
Hg(tbp) ₂ Cl ₂	1.51–1.59 (2H, <i>q</i> , <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, ³ C); 1.82 (4H, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 8.4 Hz, ² C, ⁴ C); 3.85 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 4.21 Hz, ⁵ C); 4.49 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 4.1 Hz, ¹ C); 7.24–7.48 (5H, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 9.12 Hz)
Hg ₂ (tbp) ₂ I ₄	1.61–1.65 (2H, <i>m</i> , ³ C); 1.84–1.87 (4H, <i>m</i> , ² C, ⁴ C); 3.84–3.88 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 4.2 Hz, ⁵ C); 4.32–4.38 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 4.2 Hz, ¹ C); 7.40–7.50 (5H of phenyl ring, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 10 Hz)
Hg(mtbp) ₂ l ₂	1.57–1.68 (2H, <i>q</i> , <i>J</i> 3.85 Hz, ³ C); 1.86 (4H, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 4.25 Hz, ² C, ⁴ C); 3.65 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 3.51 Hz, ⁵ C); 4.25 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 3.28 Hz, ¹ C); 3.82 (3H, <i>s</i>); 6.95 (2H of phenyl proton adjacent to OCH ₃ , <i>d</i> , <i>J</i> 31.12 Hz); 7.42 (2H of adjacent to thioamide group, <i>d</i> , <i>J</i> 30.5 Hz)
Hg ₂ (mtbp) ₂ l ₄	1.58–1.68 (2H, <i>q</i> , <i>J</i> 3.91 Hz, ³ C); 1.88 (4H, <i>m</i> , <i>J</i> 4.18 Hz, ² C, ⁴ C); 3.68 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 3.54 Hz, ⁵ C); 4.26 (2H, <i>t</i> , <i>J</i> 3.21 Hz, ¹ C); 3.81 (3H of methoxy proton, <i>s</i>); 6.96 (2H of phenyl proton adjacent to OCH ₃ , <i>d</i> , <i>J</i> 31.11 Hz); 7.46 (2H of adjacent to thioamide group, <i>d</i> , <i>J</i> 30.6 Hz)

where, *s* = singlet, *d* = doublet, *t* = triplet, *m* = multiplet, *q* = quintate.

of thioamide sulphur in bond formation. The piperidine group ¹H NMR signals observed (Table 2) for ligand suggested chair configuration of piperidine ring with two protons adjacent to thioamide near sulphur (δ 4.35) and two away from thioamide group sulphur (δ 3.55)¹⁷. In complexes the piperidine ring ³C proton (2H) signals are not different than those of ²C, ⁴C proton (4H) signals. This suggested inversion of piperidine ring from chair to boat form on coordination in complexes with (mtbp) also. The tentative structure of complexes is suggested as shown Figs. 3 and 4.

M = Cd, Hg; X = Cl, Br, I or NCS; Y = H or CH_3O -

Fig. 3

M = Cd, Hg; X = Cl, Br, I; Y = H or CH_3O -

Fig. 4

Thermal studies :

The DTA and TGA of some [$Hg LX_2$] and [$Hg L_2 X_2$] ($L = \text{tbp}$ or mtbp and $X = \text{Cl, Br}$ or I) type of complexes were carried out in the temperature range of 20–700 °C at a heating rate of 10°/min. At higher temperature the complexes decomposed in three to four endothermic steps. The TGA and DTA studies of $Hg L_2 X_2$ ($L = \text{tbp}$ or mtbp and $X = \text{Cl, Br}$ or I) indicate the loss of one ligand molecule in the temperature range 240–290 °C with an endothermic peak between 250 and 275 °C. The monoligated product $Hg LX_2$ formed with thermal loss of one ligand molecule is stable below 300 °C above which decomposition starts with an endothermic peak in the temperature range 300–330 °C. The weight of residual products at 300–330 °C corresponds to composition $Hg_2 LX_4$ which further decomposes between 350 and 450 °C with an endothermic peak in the range 360–400 °C. The decomposed products sublimed completely below 450–600

°C with a small endothermic peak near 450–460 °C. The complete loss of weight indicated the formation of metallic mercury and HgX_2 due to decomposition at high temperature. The monoligated complexes [$Hg LX_2$] ($X = \text{Cl, Br}$ or I) are also stable below their melting points but start dissociating above 240 °C with an endothermic peak between 275–300 °C with the formation of $Hg_2 LX_4$ type of products in the temperature range 300–330 °C. The intermediate product slowly decomposes and sublims in the temperature range 330–450 °C with endothermic peaks at 360–380 and ~450 °C. The compound decomposes and sublims completely below 600 °C with negligible residual mass. The TGA-DTA curve of some complexes is shown in Figs. 5 and 6 and TGA-DTA data of some complexes are recorded in Table 3.

Fig. 5

(—) [$Hg(\text{tbp})_2\text{Cl}_2$]; (---) [$Hg(\text{mtbp})\text{I}_2$]

Fig. 6

Table 3. TGA-DTA data of complexes

Compd.	Dissociation or decomposition temp. range (°C)	Product after decomposition	% Wt. loss Obsd. (Calcd.)	Transition temp. (°C)	Nature of DTA peak
Hg(tbp) ₂ Cl ₂	(i) 240–290	Hg(tbp)Cl ₂	30.07 (30.00)	250–275	Endothermic
	(ii) 300–330	Hg ₂ (tbp)Cl ₄	45.10 (45.00)	320–330	"
	(iii) 350–450	HgCl ₂	60.00 (60.01)	360–400	"
	(iv) 460–620	Hg sublime	95–98 (100)	460	"
Hg(tbp) ₂ Br ₂	(i) 250–295	Hg(tbp)Br ₂	27.00 (26.9)	260–275	Endothermic
	(ii) 300–330	Hg ₂ (tbp)Br ₄	40.00 (39.9)	320–325	"
	(iii) 350–440	HgBr ₂	53.10 (53.19)	370–390	"
	(iv) 460–620	Hg sublime	95–98 (100)	480	"
Hg(tbp)Cl ₂	(i) 270–330	Hg ₂ (tbp)Cl ₄	21.30 (21.50)	310	Endothermic
	(ii) 350–450	HgCl ₂	41.00 (40.88)	360–400	"
	(iii) 450–600	Hg sublime	96–99 (100)	460	"
Hg(mtbp) ₂ Cl ₂	(i) 250–285	Hg ₂ (mtbp)Cl ₄	30.50 (30.06)	270	Endothermic
	(ii) 310–340	Hg ₂ (mtbp)Cl ₄	48.00 (47.5)	320	"
	(iii) 360–450	HgCl ₂	77.00 (76.8)	395	"
	(iv) 450–600	Hg sublime	95–100 (100)	460	"
Hg(mtbp)I ₂	(i) 300–345	Hg ₂ (mtbp)I ₄	17.50 (17.10)	320	Endothermic
	(ii) 360–450	HgI ₂	34.2 (34.00)	380–385	"
	(iii) 470–630	Hg sublime	98–100 (100)	490	"
Hg(mtbp) ₂ I ₂	(i) 245–290	Hg(mtbp)I ₂	25.50 (25.40)	260–270	Endothermic
	(ii) 310–340	Hg ₂ (mtbp)I ₄	38.00 (38.10)	320	"
	(iii) 360–450	HgI ₂	51.00 (50.80)	380–385	"
	(iv) 470–630	Hg sublime	98–100 (100)	490	"

Experimental

Preparation of ligands :

The ligands were prepared by reported method¹⁸. Metal salts used were AR grade reagents of BDH. The molecular weight of some complexes were determined by ebullioscopic method in benzene or by Rast's camphor method. The elemental analysis, electrical conductance measurement, IR spectra were determined as reported earlier¹⁹. The ¹H NMR spectra of ligands and some complexes were recorded on FTNMR 360. The TGA and DTA of complexes were performed on a Lineis Tape L40/390 system in temperature range 20–700 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min in static air using Al₂O₃ as a reference material. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method, Cd as oxinate²⁰ and Hg as sulphide (HgS) by the procedure suggested by Volhard²¹.

Preparation of complexes :

[Cd₂(tbp)₂X₄] and [Hg₂L₂X₄] (L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br or I) :

About 5 mmol of appropriate metal salt (MX₂) (M = Cd or Hg and X = Cl, Br or I) in 50–60 ml hot methanol was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion (5 mmol) of ligand on a steam bath to get a clear solution. From resulting clear solution cream white or light cream coloured crystalline complexes separated slowly on cooling. The product was collected on filter and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂ (yield : 80–90%).

[CdL₂X₂] and [HgL₂X₂] (L = tbp or mtbp and X = Cl, Br, I or NCS) :

About 5 mmol of appropriate metal salt solution in 50–60 ml dry hot methanol (as solid in case of HgI₂ or HgBr₂) was refluxed with 10 mmol of ligand dissolved in

30–40 ml hot methanol for 30–40 min when clear solution was formed. From hot clear solution a light cream coloured precipitate began to separate which redissolved on refluxing for two hours to get clear solution. The resulting solution was concentrated on a steam bath to 20–25 ml and allowed to stand overnight when cream coloured crystalline complexes separated. The product were collected on a filter, washed with a little cold methanol and dried over CaCl_2 . The yield of product was 90–95%.

The complexes were recrystallised from hot ethanol-chloroform mixture. The analytical results, colour, molecular weight and melting point of recrystallised complexes are recorded in Table 1.

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